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Work Environment, Academic Staff job performance and Students Academic Performance in Tertiary Institutions, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined the impact of work environment on academic staff job performance and students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper is a review paper that depend secondary data. The secondary data were collected from print and online publications. The paper concluded that work environment has great impact on academic staff job performance and students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper specifically noted that work environment serve has motivating factors that propelled both academic staff and students to perform well in the institutions. Based on this findings, the paper recommend that government should create a conducive work environment through the provision of adequate modern infrastructure facilities in all tertiary institutions. Governments should increase salaries academic staff in the institutions.

Keywords: Academic performance, Academic staff job performance, Work Environment

Introduction

Tertiary education as a planned and organized educational system designed for the total development of man/woman and for the total transformation of the society through the utilization of teaching, research and provision of community service (Ogunode, Edinoh & Okolie (2023). Tertiary institution can also be seen as a subset of the general society that is made of collection of different people, different culture, different life style and different value (Ogunode & Odo 2023). The term tertiary or higher education in Nigeria is used to refer to the education obtained in higher institutions. It is however accepted by most stakeholders that the importance of higher education lies in the fact that it imparts in-depth knowledge, understanding, and professionalism that seem to advance the students to new frontiers of performance, achievement and attitudes in different aspects of life and engagements (Olorundare, 2014).

Tertiary education is defined by National policy on Education (2013) as the education given after Post Basic Education in institutions such as Universities and Inter-University Centres such as the Nigeria French Language Village, Nigeria Arabic Language Village, National Institute of Nigerian Languages, institutions such as Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEIs), and Colleges of Education, Monotechnics, Polytechnics, and other specialized institutions such as Colleges of Agriculture, Schools of Health and Technology and the National Teachers' Institutes (NTI). Tertiary education deals with implementation of teaching, research and provision of community service (Ogunode, & Onakoya. 2024; Ogunode, Peter. & Ayoko, 2023; Ogunode, & Adah Samuel 2022; Ogunode, & Ukozor 2022).

According to Ogunode, et al (2023) the goals or objectives of tertiary education includes; to aid production of manpower; to ensure national unity; to ensure technological development; to foster national unity and international peace; to increase production through research; to provide post-secondary school education; to prepare students with quality knowledge and reliable skills for independent living and the world of work. The goals of tertiary education according to the FGN National Policy on Education (2013), shall be to: contribute to national development through high-level manpower training; provide accessible and affordable quality learning opportunities in formal and informal education in response to the needs and interests of all Nigerians; provide high-quality career counselling and lifelong learning programmes that prepare students with the knowledge and skills for self-reliance and the world of work; reduce skill shortages through the production of skilled manpower relevant to the needs of the labour market; promote and encourage scholarship, entrepreneurship and community service; forge and cement national unity; and promote national and international understanding and interaction.

The realization of the objectives of tertiary education depends on availability of conducive work environment and other related factors. Ruchi & Surinder (2014) describe work environment as comprising of: physical scenery (e.g. noise, equipment, heat); fundamentals of the job itself (e.g. workload, task, complexity); extensive business features (e.g. culture, history); and even extra business background (e.g. industry setting, workers relation). Bello (2018) explained that, work environment includes a friendly, well-designed, safe physical space, good equipment and influence effective communication, which will improve productivity.

Cephas, Gibson & Bolaji , (2018) has often served as an incentive for organizations to excessively redesign the physical work environment, as it is a simple and practical improvement to carry out. Although the physical work environment is designed to encourage certain behavior. Physical environment affect how employees in an organization interact, perform tasks, and are led. Physical environment as an aspect of the work environment has directly affected the human sense and also changed interpersonal interactions and thus productivity.

The academic staff and the students are strong component of the tertiary institutions. They carry out their functions on the institutions' environment. The realization of the academic staff and the students programme and works appear to depend on the condition of the environment. It has been observed that the environment of many tertiary institutions in Nigeria are not conducive to support the academic staff and students to can out their respective functions. It is based on this that this paper seeks to examine the impact of work environment on academic staff job performance and students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literatures

Work Environment

Work environment comprises the totality of forces, actions and other influential factors that are currently and, or potentially contending with the employee's activities and performance. Work environment is the sum of the interrelationship that exists within the employees and between the employees and the environment in which the employees work (Kohun, 1992). Work environment as a milieu atmosphere, culture, tone, feel or the internal quality of an organization especially as experienced by its members and even noticed by visitors to the organization (Durotolu 2000; Sadiku 2017). Work environment is designed to produce specific performance outcomes, one space can be designed specifically to increase productivity, (Waber, 2014)

Work environment can be identified as the place that one works which means the milieus around a person' (Manu 2015). Work environment include a 'friendly, well designed, safe physical space, good equipment and effective communication which will improve productivity' (Hay 2007). Alonge, Onnoh, Olusesean, Ojo & Nathaniel, (2020) maintained that a peaceful environment devoid of rancour and where there is unity and cooperation provides avenue for motivation. The other extreme where there is intrigue, rumour mongering and discord do not support motivation. An atmosphere of uncertainty is inversely related to motivation. It is the duty of management to prevent these negative environment tendencies from disrupting the tone and subsequent staff motivation in their organisations. Apart from the psycho-social environment, the physical environment in terms of its beauty and comfort could be a source of satisfaction and motivation.

Poorly planned, unhealthy and dirty work environment cannot be a source of motivation to teachers in the school system. Well-cut lawns, beautiful flowers and building structures has been known to make teachers and students proud. Thus, the physical structures and biological environments are important in providing a measure of satisfaction and motivation to workers (Alonge, et al 2020).

Academic Staff job performance

Academic staff job performance is the total performance of teaching, researching and community services responsibilities an academic staff has carried out and still carrying out in the institutions where he or she work at a particular time. Academic staff job performance is the general record of tasks carried out by an academic staff to be compare to the assigned responsibilities and functions given to them (Ogunode & Ibrahim 2023). Academic staff job performance can also be seen as the measuring of a specific and general tasks given to faculty in an institutions and they are expected to carry them out within a specific timeline (Ogunode, et al 2023; Ogunode & Eimuhi, 2023). Academic performance from a societal stand point. The author proved this point through his work by examining strong link between academic staff performance and the quality of society. Academic staff performance as a function of excellence leadership on the part of the university management. Achieving both individual and organization excellence is a pathway through which the society and members therein accomplish their goals (Simon 2002). Academic

staff job performance constitutes all activities and functions it is expected of an academic to execute within a specific time (Ogunode, ThankGod & Olatunde-Aiyedun 2022).

Academic staff are faculty members that are key components of tertiary institutions, especially the universities. The role of academic staff in the development of higher institutions cannot be underestimated because the academic staff are the implementers of instruction in educational institutions. Academic staff as the name implies are professionals who handle the teaching, and research programmes of higher institutions and also perform other academic services (Ogunode, Jegede, & Abubakar, 2020).

Students' Academic Performance

Ogunode & Josiah, (2023) defined academic performance of students as the total learning outcome of the students in the educational institutions which includes the knowledge, social and communication skills and ideas acquired and retained through their course of study. Academic performance refers to all organized educational program and knowledge a learner or student achieves or acquires in the school environment as a result of academic activities. Academic performance as effective teaching and learning that is anchored on developmental resources with a high impact community service, creativity, and innovativeness. Academic staff performance could be measured by the acquisition of self-independent economic skills by graduates of universities (Ofoegbu & Alonge 2016). Academic staff performance relates to both practical and theoretical knowledge acquired in key professions and/or industries, including high moral discipline by both staff and students of tertiary institutions (Ofoegbu & Alonge, 2016). Similarly, Foster and Young (2004) conceptualized student academic performance as the parameter for determining the worth and carrying capacities of the students.

Oloyede (2008) classified students' assessment into three areas (i) cognitive (ii) affective and (iii) psychomotor. The first type of assessment is typically academic. The second is adjustment while the third entails the development of motor skills. Furthermore, students' academic performance is the achievement of student learning, mastery of curriculum and acquisition of social skills that help students to become useful and relevant in their respective societies. Oloyede (2008), observed that the level of academic skill necessary for successful entry into the present day job market, with or without a university education, has risen to the point that a focus on achieving academic success is necessary for all students throughout every year of schooling from nursery/primary to the university level.

Impact of Work Environment on Academic Staff job performance

A study by Dabara. Soladoye, Omotehinse, Lawal, & Asa, (2019) that examined the relationship between work environment and the level of productivity of lecturers in selected higher Institutions in Osun State Nigeria revealed that there is strong positive significant relationship of 0.965 with a P value of 0.000 between work environment and lecturers productivity in the study area. In Kenya by Nzoka (2015) found out that work environment impacted positively on work' job performance. Manu (2015), did a study in Ghana on work environment of an organization and revealed that work environment of an organization has positive impact on the productivity of its workers. A study by Awan and Tahir (2015) in Pakistan discovered that factors like supervisor support relation with co- workers, training and development and fast incentives at workplace are helpful in developing a working environment that has positive impact on employees' level of productivity. Naharuddin (2013), in a study conducted in Malaysia to investigate the effect of workplace environment's on employee's performance found that job aid and physical workplace environment are important towards having employee's performance for better productivity.

Salau, Worlu, Osibanjo, Adeniji, Falola, Olokundun, Ibidunni, Atolagbe, ,Dirisu & Ogueyungbo, (2020) investigated how work environments affect academic staff retention at public universities in southern Nigeria. The findings showed that promotions were granted based on favouritism and

'godfatherism'. The paper also revealed that compensation has a substantial impact on staff retention. Kasule (2016) did a study and discovered that unfavorable work environment negatively impacts on academics' job performance. Cephas, Gibson & Bolaji (2018) did a study and concluded that, the physical work environment has a far reaching influence on the morale of Academic Staff. When staff environment is shabby, depressing and dejected, it reduces employees' morale while the provision of good physical working environment generates interest and increases productivity. Provision of good physical working environment, that is conducive, pleasant and comfortable increases staff productivity.

Impact of Work Environment on and Students Academic Performance

Femi (2019) discovered that there was no significant relationship between environment and students' academic performance. Osuji (2016) studied the impact of school facilities on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Giwa, Zaira education zones, Kaduna State, Nigeria and found out that school facilities has impact on students' academic performance. Also, Ogunode & Edet, (2023) disclosed that facilities provided in the universities could serve as potent indicator for measuring the quality and standard of students' academic performance. The provision of conducive learning environment influence positive academic performance of students. The relationship between the two variables was positive but not statistically significant (Femi, 2019). A study by Fagbohunka (2017) that underscores the infrastructural facility and the student's academic performance in Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria. The paper has found out a positive relationship between the student's academic performance, power supply and health facilities. However, the internet facilities and transportation facilities were not adequate, whereas water supply was adequate. A test of the impact of infrastructural facility on the student's academic performance, using a Chi Square statistical technique revealed a significant value of 177.1 at 0.05 % level.

Findings

The paper found out that work environment has great impact on academic staff job performance and students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper specifically noted that work environment serve has motivating factors that propelled both academic staff and students to perform well in the institutions.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper examined the impact of work environment on academic staff job performance and students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper concluded that work environment has great impact on academic staff job performance and students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper specifically noted that work environment serve has motivating factors that propelled both academic staff and students to perform well in the institutions.

Based on this findings, the paper recommend that government should create a conducive work environment through the provision of adequate modern infrastructure facilities in all tertiary institutions. Governments should increase salaries academic staff in the institutions.

Hence it is recommended that government, proprietors, education regulatory bodies and all stakeholders in the academia should ensure that conducive work environment is provided to motivate lecturers to increase their level of productivity.

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